

Human papillomavirus-based cervical screening and long-term cervical cancer risk: a randomised health-care policy trial in Sweden

1. Article summary

Introduction

Cervical screening, endorsed by the WHO to eliminate cervical cancer, is shifting globally to primary HPV DNA testing due to its superior protection against invasive cancer compared to cytology. While many countries have adopted HPV-based screening, some still use cytology.

To validate findings from controlled trials, real-life randomized health-care policy trials are crucial. In Sweden's capital region, such a trial was being conducted from 2014 to 2017, comparing cytology-based screening with HPV-based screening with cytology triaging. The trial concluded in 2017 when Sweden implemented a national program aligned with EU guidelines.

The trial's implementation and baseline findings on detection rates of high-grade lesions for the two policies have already been published. This study aimed to assess which screening policy—cytology-based or HPV-based—offered better protection against invasive cervical cancer over an 8-year follow-up period, encompassing two full screening rounds.

Methods

Study design and participants - A randomized health-care policy trial was conducted in the cervical screening program in Sweden's Greater Stockholm region from Sept. 1, 2014, to Sept. 30, 2016. Women aged 30–64 (395,319 individuals) were randomly assigned to cytology-based screening with HPV triage (183,120) or HPV-based screening with cytology triage (212,199), using their personal identification numbers (PIN) for unbiased randomization.

Screening intervals were 3 years long for women aged 23–50 and 5 years long for those aged 51–64. Women who did not attend after an invitation received annual reminders. Coverage data showed 74% had a test during the recommended interval, but only 49% attended after the first invitation. The baseline test was the first test after the initial invitation, and follow-up spanned 8 years, encompassing two screening rounds.

The study analyzed invasive cervical cancer cases in Sweden using data from the Swedish National Quality Register of Gynecological Cancers (ICD code C53) and linked it to a research database using unique personal identification numbers. Death and emigration were identified as censoring events through the Swedish Total Population Registry. Screening data, including invitations, laboratory results, and histopathology, were obtained from the NKCx registry.

Analysis Details:

-Follow-Up Period: From the first screening invitation (intention-to-screen) or first test after invitation (per-protocol) until invasive cervical cancer diagnosis, death, emigration, or Dec 31, 2022. Women with prior diagnoses were excluded.

- Statistical Methods:

- Kaplan–Meier survival functions and cumulative incidence proportions (1–Kaplan–Meier) were calculated with 95% confidence intervals.

- Log-rank tests assessed differences between HPV and cytology screening policies.

- Cox regression models estimated hazard ratios (HRs) comparing the policies.

- Results included cumulative incidence and incidence rates per 100,000 person-years for women testing positive or negative at baseline.

- Software: SAS 9.4 and Stata BE 18.

- Ethics: Approved by Stockholm’s regional ethical review board. Consent was implicit by participation, aligning with routine health-care practices.

The trial was powered for non-inferiority in detecting high-grade cervical abnormalities at baseline, without a separate Data Safety Monitoring Board, relying on standard healthcare safety procedures.

Collection and Procedures

Cervical screening samples were collected by trained midwives using ThinPrep (Hologic), with cytology tests read by professional cytopathologists. HPV testing utilized the Roche Cobas 4800 platform, detecting HPV types 16, 18, and 12 other high-risk types.

HPV policy: HPV-positive women underwent cytology triaging. Those with abnormalities (ASCUS+) were referred for colposcopy and biopsy. HPV-positive women with normal cytology were retested after 3 years; if still positive, they were referred for colposcopy regardless of cytology results.

Cytology policy: Women with HSIL+ were directly referred for colposcopy. ASCUS/LSIL cases were triaged with HPV testing, with HPV-positive individuals referred for colposcopy and HPV-negative individuals retested after 3 years.

By Jan. 1, 2017, Sweden adopted HPV-based screening nationally for all women aged 30 and older, rendering continued cytology screening unethical. This resulted in one randomized screening round during 2014–16, followed by a second screening round under national HPV-based guidelines during 2017–23.

Outcomes

The primary outcome was the relative rate of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 2 or higher (CIN2+), reported in prior publications. The secondary outcome was long-term protection against invasive cervical cancer.

Data sources and statistical analysis

The study analyzed invasive cervical cancer in Sweden using data from the Swedish National Quality Register of Gynecological Cancers (ICD code C53), linked to trial databases via personal identification numbers. Death and emigration were identified through the Total Population Registry, and screening data came from NKCx.

Key Points:

- Follow-Up: Women were tracked from their first screening invitation (intention-to-screen) or first test (per-protocol) until cancer diagnosis, death, emigration, or Dec 31, 2022. Women with prior cancer diagnoses were excluded.
- Statistical Methods:
 - Kaplan–Meier survival analysis to compare HPV and cytology policies.
 - Cox regression models for hazard ratios (HRs).
 - Cumulative incidence and incidence rates were reported per 100,000 person-years for baseline test results.
 - Log-rank tests assessed differences; proportional hazard assumptions were verified.
- Ethics and Trial Design:
 - Approved by Stockholm's ethical review board (2011/1298-31/3); consent implied by participation.
 - Trial followed healthcare safety monitoring; major adverse events included unnecessary colposcopies and histopathology.
 - Protocol registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT01511328) and filed with Sweden's Ethical Review Agency in 2011.
- Pending Analyses: Stratified analyses by age and histopathology were post-hoc; cost data collection remains incomplete.

RESULTS

The study compared the outcomes of HPV-based screening with cytology-based screening for cervical cancer over multiple screening rounds. Attendance in the initial round was higher in the HPV-based policy, and while still higher in the second round, the difference narrowed slightly. Women who had participated in the first round showed marginally lower reattendance in the HPV-based policy compared to the cytology-based policy.

Women in the HPV policy with a baseline negative HPV test had significantly lower risk of cervical cancer during follow-up compared to women with normal baseline cytology results (HR 0.14, 95% CI 0.07–0.28). The incidence rate of cervical cancer over eight years was notably lower among HPV-negative women (1.3 per 100,000 person-years) compared to cytology-negative women (9.1 per 100,000 person-years). Among HPV-positive women, those with concurrent cytology-negative results were at the highest risk of incident cervical cancer, particularly those testing positive for HPV 16 or HPV 18. Persistent HPV positivity was observed in approximately 53.3% of women with HPV 16 or HPV 18 and 39.5% with other oncogenic HPV types.

Adverse events, including referrals for colposcopy with biopsy, were higher in the HPV-based screening group than in the cytology group. In the HPV-based policy, most incident cervical cancers arose among HPV 16 or HPV 18-positive women with normal cytology triage, underscoring the need for robust follow-up strategies in this subgroup.

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WHO International Standards for antibodies to HPV6 HPV11 HPV31 HPV33 HPV45 HPV52 and HPV58

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3. Journal

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